

ANTHROPOCENTRIC PROVERBS AS AN OBJECT OF AN
AXIOLOGICAL MIXTURE

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7481388>

Djumaniyazova Zilola Navfal qizi

Uzbekistan State World Languages University

Annotation: *In this article, several proverbs from English, Uzbek and Russian folk proverbs with a female character were analyzed. It artistically depicts the chastity, honor and femininity of English, Uzbek and Russian women.*

Key words: *proverb, modesty, generosity, character, folklore, national paremiology, woman, words of wisdom.*

Paremiological units have a great axiological potential, since they contain evaluative information about a person and his qualities, properties of objects and phenomena of the surrounding reality, predetermine actions and behavior, regulate the normativity of all aspects of life in relationship and interaction with a person: an object - a person, an action - man. Compliance with the described norms is an indispensable condition for maintaining the integrity of society. There are especially many proverbs in folklore relating to various kinds of relationships between people [1,19].

According to R.A. Khazhokova and E.A. Khazhokova, the means of contacting people is “communication, therefore, in paroemias, speech interactions, requirements for building and conducting a communicative process are comprehensively covered”. Proverbs and sayings not only accumulate knowledge and ideas that are universal for all mankind, but also reflect the national-specific worldview of a particular ethnic group. The meaning of proverbs and sayings is directly related to the division, categorization of the continuum of the surrounding world, they form an emotional and evaluative attitude towards this world.

Features of communication as one of the components of the culture of the people are directly reflected in the treasury of national paremiology [2,383]. All these give us reason to consider paremiological units as an object of study of linguistic axiology.

As the results of the study of the paremiological (phraseological) fund of Ya.A. Pavlishcheva, it reflects and consolidates the national and cultural stereotypes of a particular people, through the reproduction of the basic patterns of a certain linguistic picture of the world, the mentality of the people is expressed. At the same time, the cultural significance of the images of phraseological units can be fully disclosed, provided that these images are correlated with categories, concepts, mythologemes, stereotypes and standards of national culture (material, social or spiritual) culture and its interpretation [3,65]. In the light of such a presentation of the issue, it seems reasonable to us to say that within the framework of the language picture of the world, “the fund of proverbs of the national language makes up its own picture of the world, called paremiological” [4,24].

For example, English-language proverbs reflect such national and cultural gender stereotypes of the English people as “anthropocentrism, the tendency for male dominance over female, the opposition of female cunning and deceit to male strength and directness, the predominance of a woman over a man due to her cunning, the threat from a woman due to her exposure to emotions and because of this, the man’s fear of losing control of his life in general”. At the same time, in some phraseological units, there is a tendency to level the oppositional duality of a man and a woman. As anthropocentrism, the tendency for male dominance over female, the opposition of female cunning and deceit to male strength and directness, the predominance of a woman over a man due to her cunning, the threat from a woman due to her exposure to emotions, and because of this, the man's fear of losing control of his life in general, are all gender stereotypes that are

reflected in English-language proverbs. The opposing dualism of a man and a woman, however, has a tendency to be leveled in some phraseological units [5,65].

Consequently, a woman is one of the significant values in the system of national and cultural values of the people.

In our opinion, two provisions put forward by Ya.A. Pavlishcheva. The first provision concerns the fact that “phraseologisms, being fixed in the linguistic picture of the world, are also a source (or “database”), in which the human consciousness draws those images that it can rely on when forming its own image of reality”.

And the second provision is that “stereotypes rooted in phraseology can set certain behavioral forms for a person who has not yet taken responsibility on his own and critically comprehend what is happening to him”. In these two provisions, it seems to us, all the axiological loading and significance of paremiological units are most capaciously and fully indicated.

THE LIST OF USED LITERATURE:

1. Сайфуллина Э.Р. Когнитивная сфера русских и татарских паремий: «образ языка» и нормы речевого поведения: Автореф. дисс... канд. филол. наук. – Уфа, 2009. – С. 9.
2. Хажокова Р.А., Хажокова Э.А. Сравнительно-сопоставительный анализ пословиц и поговорок, выражающих отношение к женщине в русской и французской лингвокультурах. // Научный альманах. – Тамбов, 2015. – № 11-5 (13). – С. 383.
3. Павлицева Я.А. Фразеология как источник гендерных стереотипов (на материале английского языка). // Наукові праці. Філологія. Мовознавство. – Миколаїв, 2014. – Т. 221, № 209. – С. 65.

4. Бредис М.А. Представления о денежных отношениях в пословицах (на материале русского, латышского, литовского, немецкого и английского языков): Дисс. ...канд. филол. наук. – М., 2017. – С. 24.
5. Павлицева Я.А. Фразеология как источник гендерных стереотипов (на материале английского языка). // Наукові праці. Філологія. Мовознавство. – Миколаїв, 2014. – Т. 221, № 209. – С. 65.